

"THE REFLECTION OF KUSHAN PERIOD CULTURAL TRADITIONS IN THE CULTURE OF NORTHERN AND WESTERN TOKHARISTAN DURING THE 5TH-7TH CENTURIES"

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Annotation: Tokharistan is a significant historical and geographical region, which has been a key branch of trade routes and held strategic importance. Although this area was occupied by various invaders throughout the centuries, it has never ceased its social, economic, and cultural development. This article provides information on the preservation of the cultural traditions of the Kushan period in the material culture of Northern and Western Tokharistan during the 5th-7th centuries, and the formation of a new culture under its influence.

Keywords: Bactria - Tokharistan, Kushan Shahr, Chinese Sources, Cultural Heritage, Urbanism, Pottery, Fine Art, Sculpture, Palace.

The term *Tokharistan*, officially mentioned in written sources from 383 AD as a country, originates from the 2nd century BC, specifically the fourth quarter of the century, when it was associated with the Tocharians—one of the ethnic groups that occupied the Greek-Bactrian Kingdom. The Tocharians, according to recent studies, are the ancient Indian name of the "Great or Greater Yuezhi." In turn, the "Greater Yuezhi" or Tocharians are identified as the Oghuz Turks. Initially an ethnic name, the term *ethnonym* began to refer to the name of the country where they settled from 383 AD onward. The primary sources regarding the country of Tokharistan include the *Bei Shi* (covering events from 386–618 AD), *Sui Shu* (written in the second half of the 7th century, covering events from 581–618 AD), and *Tan Shu*, as well as the accounts of the Chinese traveler and Buddhist monk Xuanzang (633–645 AD) and the historian Hou Chao. According to these sources, the boundaries of Tokharistan extended from the "Iron Gate" in the Boysun Mountains in the north to the foothills of the Hindu Kush in the south, spanning 1000 li (1 li equals approximately 0.5–0.2 km). In the east-west direction, it extended from the Pamir Mountains to the borders of the Sassanian Empire in Iran, covering a distance of 3000 li [Пугаченкова, Ртвеладзе, 1990, С. 123.]

In the second half of the 3rd century, as a result of powerful conflicts and severe tragedies within the Kushan Empire, the Kushans became subordinate to the Sassanid Empire of Persia. Consequently, the Kushan-Sassanid (Kushan Shahr) province was established, with the Kushan territories (mainly Bactria) coming under the control of the Sassanids.

The history and culture of early medieval Northern Tokharistan have been studied by archaeological scholars such as M.E. Masson, B.A. Litvinskiy, V.V. Solovyov, G.A. Pugachenkova, E.V. Rtveldze, L.I. Albaum, V.V. Bartold, V.V. Tomashek, V.M. Masson, B. Gafurov, A.M. Belinitskiy, S. Khmelnitskiy, and T.J. Annayev. The archaeological study of early medieval monuments in this region is associated with the activities of the Termez Archaeological Complex Expedition from 1936 to 1938. The discovery of the Ayrptom friezes in 1932 served as the impetus for the establishment of this expedition, and to this day, the monuments in this area continue to be regularly studied.

The culture of early medieval Tokharistan was significantly shaped by the Kushan

period. The Kushan Empire, resulting from the unification of various peoples and tribes, created a foundation for the development of a unique culture. Additionally, it positively influenced the further development of the cultural traditions of each people and facilitated closer interactions between them. Specifically, in Bactria, a distinct Bactrian artistic school was formed and flourished. The formation of this school was greatly influenced by local cultural traditions, Hellenism, Buddhism, and the nomadic peoples. [Sh. Pidayev, 2001, p. 11].

Early medieval cities, like those of the Kushan period, were primarily composed of two structural components: the *arki alo* (citadel) and the *shahriston* (town). For example, the city of Kofirqala embodied the architectural layout of Kushan period urbanism, while cities like Quloglitepa and Khosiyattepa were formed based on the settlements of the Kushan period. From the mid-6th century onward, fortresses in Northern Tokharistan began to adopt the Kushan period design (e.g., Oqtepa), featuring a central corridor with adjoining side rooms.

V. A. Nilsen, who studied the early medieval architecture of Southern Uzbekistan, identified three groups of settlements. The first group consists of large villages composed of feudal (landowner peasant) fortresses and adjacent residential buildings. The second group includes the fortresses of individual large feudal landowners, such as Bolaliktepa and Jumalaktepa. The third group comprises the separate dwellings of ordinary peasants [Нильсен, 1964, С. 177-184, Нильсен, 1966, С. 140-176.]. In the works of B.A. Litvinskiy, B.Ya. Staviskiy, and Sh. Pidayev, the typology of Kushan settlements is based on size and is divided into four categories: those with an area of up to one hectare; those ranging from 2 to 5 hectares; those ranging from 6 to 15 hectares; and those covering more than 15 hectares [Литвинский, 1973, С. 99-125, Ставиский, 1982, С.42-44].

Currently, four stratigraphic scales have been developed for the pottery of Northern Bactria: "Qobadiyon," "Dalvarzin," "Kholchayon," and "Yovon" (Зеймаль

Т., 1969). Flat, vertical-ringed, rimmed, and semi-spherical bowls, polished one-handled and two-handled mugs, as well as wide-rimmed kitchenware, are characteristic of the Kushan period. The tradition of producing semi-spherical and rimmed bowls continued into the early medieval period. However, by this time, compared to Kushan-period pottery, the quality of the produced vessels significantly declined, and the proportion of vessels made using molds increased. Additionally, the decoration of pottery deteriorated, and the production of two-handled mugs ceased. Instead, from the mid-5th century onward, one-handled, wide-rimmed, and circular mugs began to be made. These types of vessels were designed with two circular-shaped handles for ease of carrying. [Т.Аннаев, 1988, p. 67]. Unlike the Kushan period, from the early 6th century, bowls with thickened rims and angular round bottoms began to appear.

The figurines discovered at the Kuyovkurgan fortress (5th century AD), fully excavated by the Bactrian Expedition in 1977, provide sufficient information about the sculpture art of this period. The figurines, made of clay, with curly hair and various decorations, are a direct continuation of Kushan sculptural traditions. During the Kushan period, it became customary to depict members of the ruling family in sculpture. This tradition continued in later periods, and Kuyovkurgan was also a settlement for the noble farmers. Additionally, separate gypsum fragments with images were found at the fortress.

According to archaeological research, in the early medieval period, the valleys, rivers, and deserts of Tokharistan were developed, and as a result, by the late 5th century to the early 6th century, the borders of the Kushan period villages in this region were reestablished.

New cities and villages were founded, ancient irrigation systems were restored, and canals were constructed. Written sources, archaeological finds, and numismatic data indicate that the population of Tokharistan adhered to religions such as Buddhism and Zoroastrianism.

Buddhism was one of the widely practiced religions among the population during this period. According to the information provided by Xuanzang, at the beginning of the 7th century, there were five Buddhist temples in Chaganiyan, and ten in Termez. These temples housed nearly a thousand monks and contained large prayer halls (devoncha) and Buddha statues.

Additionally, in Tokharistan, a writing system with 25 characters, written from left to right, also developed. During this period, artistic expression evolved in two main directions, just like in the Kushan period: secular and religious. Examples of secular art include wall paintings depicting ritual scenes found at Bolaliktepa, hunting scenes from Tavka fortress, and statues from Kuyovkurgan. An example of religious art is the Buddha statue from Ajinatepa, which exceeds 12 meters in height.

Due to its position as a key crossroads in trade, the Tokharistan region developed strong external political and trade relations. By the middle of the 7th century, the first Arab invaders began to enter Tokharistan, and by the second half of the 8th century, the region was incorporated into the Arab Caliphate.

In conclusion, during the early medieval period, the settlements in the Surkhandarya region, due to their geographical location and the importance of the trade routes passing through them, created fertile ground for the emergence of various cultures and religions. Even though this region was conquered by states such as the Kushans, Sassanids, Hephthalites, and the Turkic Khaganate, its development did not cease.

The archaeological research conducted in the ancient cities and settlements of this region has revealed the rich heritage created by our ancestors and further demonstrates the significant contribution these regions made to the development of our ancient history.

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